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Photosensitive Ag-containing ZnO/CeO₂ Composites with non-stoichiometric matrix

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It was shown the forming of Ag-containing ZnO/CeO₂ composites occurs due to complex process of decomposition and structure transformation of oxide materials and Ag-complexes. It allows obtaining photosensitive materials with different sizes and structures in one synthesized approach. For composite nanoparticles (NPs) with size up to 30 nm the photosensitivity connected with an anomalous decreasing of band gap energies at decreasing of NPs sizes and an effective charge separation due to electron stocks on [Ce³⁺...Vo] ... [O₂] centers and surface [Ce⁴⁺...O₂⁻] oxidative centers formation. For more big NPs sizes of this composite the plasmon resonance plays more significantly role in photosensitive properties of material.

Introduction

Ag-containing photosensitive oxide composites are promising materials for chemistry, environmental media, medicine, green energy, the electronics industry and other fields [1]. Same kinds of such heterogeneous systems are using in creation of metal/oxide composite. There are Ag NPs/oxide NPs, Ag-containing shell/oxide core, Ag-rich NPs surface or bulk. These systems have enhanced determined properties, in particular optical, electrochemical, conductivity, photosensitive [2]. Properties of Ag-containing oxide composite systems depend on kind of realized structure of such material and structure of oxide host matrix. It is known, that in tetragonal zirconia Ag ions include in complex with neighbor oxygen vacancies. The investigation of Ag/Y-ZrO₂ shows the realization of Ag⁰ shell/Y-ZrO₂ core that decorated by Ag⁰ NPs [3]. Whereas the change of host zirconia matrix on alumina matrix leads to formation the Al-O-Ag bonds up to 900°C and creation of Ag NPs are not occur [4]. The investigation of Ag/CeO₂ structure shows the presence two types of silver centers in structure – Ag⁺ in host ceria and surface Ag⁰ clusters. Also, ceria matrix is non-stoichiometric because it has tend to self-formation Ce³⁺ centers in CeO₂ matrix. The feature of this system is the presence of two oxidative-reduction pair - Ag⁺/Ag and Ce³⁺/Ce⁴⁺. Introduction of Ag in other non-stoichiometric, in particular ZnO shows the formation of silver clusters on zinc oxide surface. Two last kinds of oxide are more promise materials for photocatalytic applied, in particular water splitting, organic pollutants destroying, antibacterial act, other. It is noted, that the formation of heterocatalytic systems based on

ZnO/CeO₂ matrix is interesting because the main components have:

- approximately equal band gap values - E_g(ZnO) = 3.2 eB, whole E_g(CeO₂) is about 5.5 eB, but the presence of 4f levels in band gap structure is decreased it value to 3.3 eB;
- good positions of their band gaps, it is approved charge separation in composite structure;
- the presence of component, that generate the oxidative/reduction cycles;
- the limited solubility of components into each other.

Ag-decorated ZnO/CeO₂ structure may significantly enhanced photocatalytical activity and photosensitive of material due to realization plasmon resonance condition in it. Optical spectra different Ag-decorated oxides show peak surface plasmon resonance (SPR) in range 350-600 nm. Position of SPR peak depends on as type of oxide matrix, type of realized structure (core/shell or NPs/NPs) and oxide and Ag⁰ NPs sizes. In other words, the type of oxide matrix, the temperature of the treatment and the reduction conditions may be important factors for controlling the composite morphology, charge state, dispersity of Ag NPs and properties of such complex material. In this work, the questions of creation of Ag-containing composite structure based on non-stoichiometric oxide matrixes will be discussed.

Experimental

Ag-containing ZnO/CeO₂ nanoparticles were synthesized using a precipitation technique from determined salts in ammonium solution. All used chemicals were of chemical purity. The value of the pH was more than 8. The sediments were washed

several times with distilled water before drying in a microwave furnace ($P = 700 \text{ W}$, $f = 2.45 \text{ GHz}$). The dried precipitates were calcined in a resistive furnace at 500, 700 and 900 °C with a dwell time of 2 h. The amount of Ag_2O is 1 mol. %, and amount of CeO_2 is changed from 1 to 98 mol. %. Chemical reduction of these system was carry out by glucose-ammonium solution.

The powders were characterized by means of X-ray diffraction (Dron-3) with $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ radiation for crystallite sizes and quantitative phase analyses. The optical properties of ZnO nanopowders were measured on a Cary 5000 UV-Vis-NIR spectrometer with Internal Diffuse Reflectance sphere (Agilent Technologies, USA). The electron spin resonance (ESR) investigation was carried out on ESR spectrometer CMS-8400 (Adani, Belarus) at room temperature.

Results and discussion

Fig.1 show the XRD date of Ag-containing ZnO/ CeO_2 composite with different temperature synthesis.

Fig.1 XRD date of Ag-containing ZnO/ CeO_2 composite with temperature synthesis a) 500°C, b) 900°C.

According to presented date the type and phase composition which are realized depend on as initial composition of oxides and as calcination temperature. At high concentration of ceria (above 90 mol. %) the monophasic systems are synthesized. For other compositions of Ag-containing ZnO/ CeO_2 the two or three component systems are observed.

Main phases are $\text{Ce}_{1-y}\text{Zn}_y\text{O}_{2-x}$ or $\text{Zn}_{1-z}\text{Ce}_z\text{O}_{2-x}$ in dependence from ceria amounts. It was shown that solubility zinc oxide in ceria is higher than ceria in zinc oxide, because for system with ceria up to 40 mol. % the main phase is $\text{Ce}_{1-y}\text{Zn}_y\text{O}_{2-x}$. It is noted, the chloride salts were used for synthesis and it allows to precipitation of silver as silver chloride complex (or silver chloride) that has ability to destruction at heat-treatment with creation free silver or silver oxide. There are $\text{Ce}_{1-y}\text{Zn}_y\text{Ag}_{0.01}\text{O}_{2-x}$ (I, $y < 0.1$, all temperatures), $\text{AgCl}(\text{Ag}_2\text{O}, \text{Ag})\text{Ce}_{1-y}\text{Zn}_y\text{O}_{2-x}$ (II, $0.1 < y < 0.6$, $T < 700^\circ\text{C}$), $\text{AgCl}(\text{Ag}_2\text{O}, \text{Ag})\text{Ce}_{1-y}\text{Zn}_y\text{O}_{2-x}/\text{Zn}_{1-z}\text{Ce}_z\text{O}_{2-x}$ (III, $0.4 < y < 0.6$, all temperatures) and $\text{AgCl}(\text{Ag}_2\text{O}, \text{Ag})\text{Zn}_{1-z}\text{Ce}_z\text{O}_{2-x}/\text{Ce}_{1-y}\text{Zn}_y\text{O}_{2-x}$ (IV, $y < 0.4$, all temperatures).

Fig. 2 show the influence of calcination temperature on nanoparticles sizes.

Fig. 3 Dependence of NPs sizes ($\text{Ce}_{1-y}\text{Zn}_y\text{O}_{2-x}$ or $\text{Zn}_{1-z}\text{Ce}_z\text{O}_{2-x}$) on ceria amount for system with different calcination temperatures.

According to presented date, the NPs sizes depend on as calcination temperatures and also the ceria amount in investigated systems.

Thus, we can mark four regions in which Ag-containing ZnO/ CeO_2 composites have different structures and structural characteristics, in particular NPs sizes.

It is known that nanosized CeO_2 has anomalous dependence of band gap value on NPs size up to 20 nm. Investigation of optical properties of each described above region show dependence optical properties on chemical, phase composition and NPs sizes. Practically for all systems in optical spectra the 2 direct and 1 indirect transfer in band gap. Only systems with CeO_2 amount up to 10 mol. % have 1 direct and 1 indirect transfers. Plasmon resonance is observed only for systems that were heat-treatment at 900°C. Table 1 show the characteristic values of band gap and plasmon resonance energies for structure from described above regions and which were formed at calcination temperatures $> 700^\circ\text{C}$.

Table 1 Characteristic values of band gap and plasmon resonance energies (SPR)

region	Band gap energy, eV			SPR, eV	
	direct		indirect	initial	Reduct
700°C					
I	3.7	3.4	3.2	-	2.6
III	3.8	3.4	3.0	-	2.6
IV	-	3.25	3.15	-	-
900°C					
I	3.85	3.41	3.2	2.5	2.65
III	4.0	3.36	3.1	2.5	2.78
IV	-	3.24	3.15	2.4	2.8

As we can see, the decreasing of ceria amount in composition led to increasing of energy of first direct transfer and decreasing of second direct transfer and indirect transfer. Temperature influence only on energy of first direct transfer and the presence and energy of plasmon resonance. Energy of SPR for systems (900°C) increasing with decreasing of amount ceria in systems. Increasing of energy plasmon resonance according Mi theory connected with or Ag NPs size decreasing or Ag shell thickness increasing. At reduction the amount of Ag free must increasing and core/Ag shell structure are formed. Decreasing of SPR energy with increasing of ceria may be connected with presence in these systems Ce^{3+}/Ce^{4+} redox pair. Change of amount of Ce^{3+} centers in such systems is observed, see fig. 3.

Fig. 3 ESR spectra of initial and chemical reduction structures from I and III regions, 900°C.

ESR investigations show the change of $[Ce^{3+}-V_o]$ centers ($g_{\perp}=1,9615$ та $g_{\parallel}=1,9447$). Two isotropic signals at $g=1,97$ and 1.95 may be described as defective centers connected with silver nanoclusters Ag_x^{m+} . After reduction intensity of signal from $[Ce^{3+}-V_o]$ is decreasing but the intensity from Ag_x^{m+} is increasing. Fig.4 shows ESR spectra of structures from I region.

Fig. 4 ESR spectra of initial and chemical reduction structures from I, Tcalc=700°C.

ESR spectra of these systems contains also the hyperfine structure with $g=2.032$ that corresponds to $Ce^{4+}-O_2^-$ complexes that generation from $[Ce^{3+} \dots V_o] \dots [O_2]$ at electron transfer from Ce^{3+} to O_2 . Surface of such systems has oxidative properties. The presence addition O_2^- species with oxidative properties is not allow to realization of Ag free NPs formation at heat-treatment and reduction also.

Conclusion

Thus in framework of one synthesis approach may be synthesized oxide particles with different defects structure and optical properties. These systems may be proposed as photocatalytic and photosensitive materials. The possible ways of responsive on light irradiation are discussed. It was shown that photoactivity for systems that were synthesized:

- under heat-treatment up to 700°C it is enhanced due to electron stocks on $[Ce^{3+} \dots V_o] \dots [O_2]$ and active oxygen form formation (O_2^-). It is realized the additional charge separation in such systems.
- under heat-treatment above 700°C it is enhanced due to formation core/Ag shell structure and SPR plays important role in enhanced photosensitive of these materials.

It was shown that for these composite the temperature and ceria amount are effective approach for controlling of NPs sizes, of defectiveness of complex oxide and their optical properties.

Keywords: Ag-decorated ZnO-CeO₂, photosensitive composite, structure defects.

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